

PHP DASTURLASH TILI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI

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Annontatsiya: Ushbu maqolada php dasturlash tili va uning imkoniyatlari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Dasturlash, zamonaviy, web-saytlar, tizim, texnologiya.

PHP - bu eng keng tarqalgan, zamonaviy web dasturlash tili hisoblanadi. Internetdagi saytlar va web-xizmatlarning aksariyati PHP-dan foydalangan holda yaratilgan. Ba'zi ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, PHP saytlarning 80% dan ko'prog'ida, jumladan facebook.com, vk.com, baidu.com va boshqa xizmatlarda keng qo'llaniladi. Tilning soddaligi bizga turli xil murakkablikdagi saytlar va turli xil portallarni tez va osonlik bilan yaratishimizga imkon bera oladi.

PHP- 1994- yilda daniyalik dasturchi Rasmus Lerdorf tomonida yaratilgan bo'lib, dastlab boshqa Perl tilidagi skriptlar to'plami edi. Keyinchalik ushbu skriptlar S tilidagi tarjimonga qayta yoziladi. Yaratilganidan beri PHP (PHP uchun qisqacha: Hypertext Preprocessor - PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor) web-saytlar va web-ilovalarni soddalashtirish uchun qulay vositalar to'plamini taqdim etdi.

Xosting xizmatlarining keng tarqalishi, hamda ularning arzonligi. Chunki, qoida tariqasida, xosting kompaniyalari Linux oilasining operatsion tizimlaridan birida ishlaydigan Apache yoki Nginx web-serverlarida PHP web-saytlariga joylashadilar. Ikkala web-server va Linux-ga asoslangan operatsion tizimlar bepul hisoblanadi, bu esa hostingning umumiy xarajatlarini kamaytiradi.

PHP yadro va plaginlarning mavjudligi bilan ajralib turadi, "kengaytmalar": ma'lumotlar bazalari, rozetkalar, dinamik grafikalar, kriptografik kutubxonalar, PDF hujjatlar va boshqalar bilan ishlash uchun har kim o'z kengaytmasini ishlab chiqishi va unga ulanishi mumkinligi. Yuzlab kengaytmalar mavjud, ammo standart to'plamda bir necha o'nlab yaxshi tashkil etilganlar ham mavjud. PHP tarjimoni web-serverga ushbu, server uchun maxsus yaratilgan modul orqali (masalan, Apache yoki IIS uchun) yoki CGI dasturi sifatida ulanadi.

Eng keng tarqalgan operatsion tizimlar uchun (Windows, MacOS, Linux) PHP dasturiy ta'minotini ishlab chiqish paketlarining mavjudligi, ya'ni biz ushbu operatsion tizimlarning har qandayida web-saytlar yaratishimiz mumkin.

- PHP turli web-serverlar bilan birgalikda ishlay olishi mumkin: Apache, Nginx, IIS.

- Rivojlanishning soddaligi va qulayligi. Qoida tariqasida, PHP-da dasturlash borasida kam tajribaga ega bo'lgan holda ham, biz oddiy web-saytlar yaratishimiz mumkin.

- PHP C ga o'xshash, shuning uchun S yoki sintaksis kabi sintaksisga ega tillardan birini bilsak, PHPni o'rganish biz uchun yanada osonroq bo'ladi.

PHP - ko'plab ma'lumotlar bazalari tizimlari (MySQL, MSSQL, Oracle, Postgre, MongoDB va shu kabilar) bilan ishlashni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

Xosting xizmatlarining keng tarqalishi, hamda ularning arzonligi. Chunki, qoida tariqasida, xosting kompaniyalari Linux oilasining operatsion tizimlaridan birida ishlaydigan Apache yoki Nginx web-serverlarida PHP web-saytlariga joylashadilar. Ikkala web-server va Linux-ga asoslangan operatsion tizimlar bepul hisoblanadi, bu esa hostingning umumiy xarajatlarini kamaytiradi.

Endi PHPda birinchi kichik sayt yaratamiz. Ammo uni yaratmasdan oldin, veb-saytni ishlab chiqish uchun barcha kerakli vositalarni yuklab olishimiz va o'rnatib olishimiz kerak. Bugun sizlar bilan ular haqida ma'lumotlarga ega bo'laylik. Web uchun dasturlash sohasida PHP eng sodd ssenariy tillaridan biri hisoblanadi (JSP, Perl va ASP.NETda ^^ [78]

ishlatiladigan tillar), soddaligi, bajarilish tezligi, boy funktsionalligi va PHP litsenziyasi asosida manba kodlarining tarqalishi sababli . PHP yadro va plaginlarning mavjudligi bilan ajralib turadi, "kengaytmalar": ma'lumotlar bazalari, rozetkalar, dinamik grafikalar, kriptografik kutubxonalar, PDF hujjatlar va boshqalar bilan ishlash uchun har kim o'z kengaytmasini ishlab chiqishi va unga ulanishi mumkinligi. Yuzlab kengaytmalar mavjud, ammo standart to'plamda bir necha o'nlab yaxshi tashkil etilganlar ham mavjud. PHP tarjimoni web-serverga ushbu, server uchun maxsus yaratilgan modul orqali (masalan, Apache yoki IIS uchun) yoki CGI dasturi sifatida ulanadi.

1994-yilda daniyalik dasturchi Rasmus Lerdorf o'zining onlayn rezyumeiga tashrif buyuruvchilarni namoyish qilish va kuzatib borish, HTML hujjatlar shablonlarini qayta ishlash uchun C dasturlash tilida CGI-skriptlar to'plamini yaratdi. Lerdorf shaxsiy uy-sahifasini, shaxsiy uy-sahifasi deb atagan, ammo bu nom ko'proq "PHP vositalari" deb nomlangan va tez orada funktsionallik tugadi va Rasmus PHP Tools-ni qayta yozdi va yanada katta dasturlardan birini yaratdi. 1995-yil iyun oyida Rasmus PHP Tools-ning manba kodini ommaga namoyish qildi , bu esa dasturchilarga o'zlari xohlagan tarzda foydalanishga imkon yaratib berdi. Shuningdek, bu foydalanuvchilarga koddagi xatolarni tuzatishga va uni yaxshilashga imkon bera oldi.

1997-yilda, uzoq beta-sinovdan so'ng, ishlov beruvchining C - PHP / FI 2.0 da yozilgan ikkinchi versiyasi chiqdi. Undan dunyodagi barcha Internet-domenlarning taxminan 1% (taxminan 50 ming) foydalangan hisoblanadi.

PHP 3.0 ning eng katta kuchli tomonlaridan biri shundaki, bu yadroni qo'shimcha modullar bilan kengaytirish qobiliyati edi. Keyinchalik, kengaytmalarni yozish interfeysi ko'plab uchinchi tomon ishlab chiquvchilarni o'zlarining modullari ustida ishlaydigan PHP-ga jalb qildi, bu esa PHP-ga juda ko'p sonli ma'lumotlar bazalari, protokollari bilan ishlash va ko'plab API-larni qo'llab-quvvatlash imkonini bera oldi. Ishlab chiquvchilarning ko'pligi tilning jadal rivojlanishiga va mashhurligining tez o'sishiga sabab bo'ldi. Butunlay yangi dasturlash tili, yangi nom oldi. Ishlab chiquvchilar PHP / FI-dagi shaxsiy foydalanish qo'shimchasini bekor qildilar, hamda til PHP deb o'zgartirildi.

1995- yili Rasmus PHPni o'zining HTML formalari bilan ishlaydigan boshqa dastur bilan umumlashtirib PHP/FI Version 2 ("Form Interpretator") hosil qildi. 1997- yilga borib PHP dan foydalanuvchi saytlar 50 mingdan oshdi. Shundan so'ng web texnologiya ustalari PHP g'oyasi asosida mukammal til yaratishga Ziva Suraski va Endi Gutmans asoschiligida kirishildi. PHPni samarali deb hisoblanmagani uchun deyarli noldan boshlab, mavjud C va Perl tillaridan ibrat olib PHP3 talqinini yaratildi. 1999- yilga kelib PHP asosida qurilgan saytlar milliondan oshib ketdi. 2000 yilda esa Zend Technologies shirkati yangi ko'pgina funksiyalarni qo'shgan holda PHP4 sharhlovchisini yaratdi.

PHP - web texnologiya tili. PHPni o'rganish uchun avval HTML va dasturlash tilidan habardor bo'lish talab qilinadi. HTML/CSS va JavaScript larni mukammal bilguvchilar uchun PHPni o'rganish murakkablik tug'dirmaydi. PHPning vazifasi HTML faylini yaratib berish. JavaScript yordamida bajariladigan ko'pgina operatsiyalarni PHP orqali ham amalga oshirish mumkin, ammo e'tibor qilish lozimki, PHP - serverda; JavaScript - mijoz tomonida bajariladi. PHPda yozilgan kod serverning o'zida bajarilib, mijozga HTML shaklida etib boradi. Bu havfsizlik jihatdan ancha maqsadga muvofiq. JavaScript yordamida kod yozish, ma'lumot uzatish va qabul qilishni biroz tezlashtirsa-da, kodni mijoz ko'rish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Baribir har ikkisini boshqasi bosa olmaydigan o'z o'rnini bor, ravshanki bu o'rin PHPda muhimroq va kattaroq.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini tuzatish usullari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 280-291. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1758> dan olindi.

2. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 226-238. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1752> dan olindi.
3. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 173-182. <https://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1747> dan olindi.
4. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar tizimini echishning matritsa, Gauss va Gauss-Jordan usullari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 312-322. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1761> dan olindi.
5. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va komissiya xossalari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 133-145. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1744> dan olindi.
6. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va komissiya xossalari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 146-152. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1744> dan olindi.
7. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Kvadratik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 153-172. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1746> dan olindi.
8. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 109-120. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1742> dan olindi.
9. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 183-191. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1748> dan olindi.
10. Usmonov, M. T. o'g'li. (2021). Vektorlarning vektor va aralash ko'paytmalari. Fan va ta'lim, 2(8), 271-279. <http://openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/1757> dan olindi.
11. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Teylor formulasini matematik masalalarni echishdagi ahamiyati. "«Science and Education» Scientific Journal" Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 19-23.
12. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Darajali qatorlarning taqribiy hisoblashlarga tatbiqi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 29-32.
13. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Ishoralari almashinib keluvchi qatorlar. Leybnits alomati. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 24-28.
14. Usmonov, M.T. & Shokirov.,Sh.H, (2022). Teylor qatori va uning tadbiqlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-3, 33-38.

15. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление центра тяжести плоской ограниченной фигуры с помощью двойного интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 64-71.
16. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Биномиальное распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 81-85.
17. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Поток векторного поля. Поток через замкнутую поверхность. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 52-63.
18. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление определенного интеграла по формуле трапеций и методом Симпсона. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 213-225.
19. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод касательных. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 25-34.
20. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление предела функции с помощью ряда. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 92-96.
21. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Примеры решений произвольных тройных интегралов. Физические приложения тройного интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 39-51.
22. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление двойного интеграла в полярной системе координат. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 97-108.
23. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Криволинейный интеграл по замкнутому контуру. Формула Грина. Работа векторного поля. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 72-80.
24. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Правило Крамера. Метод обратной матрицы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 249-255.
25. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Теоремы сложения и умножения вероятностей. Зависимые и независимые события. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 202-212.
26. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Распределение и формула Пуассона. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 86-91.
27. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Геометрическое распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 18-24.
28. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление площади поверхности вращения. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 97-104.
29. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Нахождение обратной матрицы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 123-130.
30. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление двойного интеграла. Примеры решений «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 192-201.

31. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод прямоугольников. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 105-112.
32. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Как вычислить длину дуги кривой?. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 86-96.
33. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Вычисление площади фигуры в полярных координатах с помощью интеграла. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 77-85.
34. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Повторные пределы. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 35-43.
35. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Дифференциальные уравнения второго порядка и высших порядков. Линейные дифференциальные уравнения второго порядка с постоянными коэффициентами. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 113-122.
36. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Пределы функций. Примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 139-150.
37. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Метод наименьших квадратов. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 54-65.
38. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Непрерывность функции двух переменных. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 44-53.
39. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Интегрирование корней (иррациональных функций). Примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 239-248.
40. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Криволинейные интегралы. Понятие и примеры решений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 26-38.
41. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Гипергеометрическое распределение вероятностей. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 19-25.
42. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Абсолютная и условная сходимость несобственного интеграла. Признак Дирихле. Признак Абеля. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 66-76.
43. Усмонов, М.Т. (2021). Решение систем линейных уравнений. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 131-138.
44. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 226-238.
45. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Teskari matritsa. Teskari matritsani hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 292-302.
46. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Том-2, 323-331.

47. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 121-132.
48. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko 'paytmasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 183-191.
49. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Xos vektorlari bazis tashkil qiluvchi chiziqli operatorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 146-152.
50. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni echish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 303-311.
51. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 173-182.
52. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Kvadratik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 153-172.
53. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 109-120.
54. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va ularning xossalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 133-145.
55. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Determinantlar nazariyasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 256-270.
56. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 280-291.
57. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Autentification, authorization and administration. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 233-242.
58. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 332-339.
59. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). EHTIMOLLAR NAZARIYASI. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-1, 10-15.
60. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni echish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 333-311.
61. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-21, 323-331.
62. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 332-339.
63. Usmonov, M.T. (2021). Chiziqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal, Tom-2, 121-132.
64. Usmonov M. T. & Qodirov F. E, BIR JINSLI VA BIR JINSLIGA OLIB KELINADIGAN DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. AMALIY MASALALARGA TADBIQI (KO'ZGU MASALASI) , BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR

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65. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li, Sayifov Botirali Zokir o'g'li, Negmatova Nilufar Ergash qizi, Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li, BIRINCHI VA IKKINCHI TARTIBLI HUSUSIY HOSILALAR. TO'LA DIFFERENSIAL. TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH, BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI: 2022: SPECIAL ISSUE: ZAMONAVIY UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI

66. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li, Sayifov Botirali Zokir o'g'li, Negmatova Nilufar Ergash qizi, Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li, IKKI ARGUMENTLI FUNKSIYANING ANIQLANISH SOHASI, GRAFIGI, LIMITI VA UZLUKSIZLIGI, BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI: 2022: SPECIAL ISSUE: ZAMONAVIY UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI

67. Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li. (2022). FURYE QATORI. FUNKSIYALARNI FURYE QATORIGA YOYISH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6055125>

68. Usmonov. M. T. ., & Qodirov. F. E. . (2022). DARAJALI QATORLAR. DARAJALI QATORLARNING YAQINLASHISH RADIUSI VA SOHASI. TEYLOR FORMULASI VA QATORI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 8–20. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1151>

69. Usmonov. M. T. ., & Qodirov. F. E.. (2022). FURE QATORI VA UNING TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 21–33. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1152>

70. M.T Usmonov, M.A Turdiyeva, Y.Q Shoniyozova, (2021). SAMPLE POWER. SELECTION METHODS (SAMPLE ORGANIZATION METHODS). ООО НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА, 59-60.

71. Усмонов, М.Т, М.А.Турдиева (2021). ГЛАВА 9. МЕТОДЫ И СРЕДСТВА СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ СЕТЕЙ. РИСКИ И ПРИНЦИПЫ ЗАЩИТЫ ИНФОРМАЦИИ В ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ ПОЧТЕ. ББК 60 С69, Ст-99.

72. Усмонов, М.Т, J.M.Saipnazarov, К.В. Ablaqulov (2021) SOLUTION OF MATHEMATICAL PROBLEMS IN LOWER CLASSES. Книга: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ, 167-177.

73. Усмонов М.Т. (2022). E-LEARNING И ЕГО РОЛЬ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. : Special Issue_Та'limni modernizatsiyalash jarayonlari muammolar va echimlar». 168-171.

74. Usmonov. M. T. , & Qodirov. F. E.. (2022). STOKS FORMULASI. SIRT INTEGRALLARI TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 34-45. Retrieved from <https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1153>
75. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR), Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 10-13.
76. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Number. The Establishment of the Concept of Natural Number and Zero. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJASIR), Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 7-9.
77. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS), Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 66-68.
78. Usmonov M. T. General Concept of Mathematics and Its History. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR). Vol. 4 Issue 12, December - 2020, Pages: 38-42
79. Usmonov M. T. Asymmetric Cryptosystems. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 6-9.
80. Usmonov M. T. Basic Concepts of Information Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 5-8.
81. Usmonov M. T. Communication Control Systems, Methodology. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 47-50.
82. Usmonov M. T. Compatibility between the Two Package Elements. Binar Relations and Their Properties. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 52-54.
83. Usmonov M. T. Cryptographic Protection of Information. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 24-26.
84. Usmonov M. T. Electronic Digital Signature. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 30-34.

85. Usmonov M. T. "Equal" And "Small" Relations. Add. Laws Of Addition. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 27-29.
86. Usmonov M. T. Establish Network Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-21.
87. Usmonov M. T. Fundamentals of Symmetric Cryptosystem. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
88. Usmonov M. T. General Concepts of Mathematics. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-16.
89. Usmonov M. T. Identification and Authentication. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 39-47.
90. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection and Its Types. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 1-4.
91. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection in Wireless Communication Systems. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 61-64.
92. Usmonov M. T. Information protection supply. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 12-15.
93. Usmonov M. T. Information Security Policy. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 70-73.
94. Usmonov M. T. Information War. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 79-82.
95. Usmonov M. T. International and National Legal Base in the Field Of Information Security. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 7-14.
96. Usmonov M. T. Legal Legislative Basis for Detection of Information Crime. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 80-87.

97. Usmonov M. T. Mathematical Proofs. Incomplete Induction, Deduction, Analogy. The Concept Of Algorithm And Its Properties. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 26-29.
98. Usmonov M. T. Means of Information Protection. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 27-30.
99. Usmonov M. T. Organization of E-Mail Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
100. Usmonov M. T. Organizing Internet Protection. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 24-28.
101. Usmonov M. T. Origin and Equal Strength Relationships between Sentences. Necessary and Sufficient Conditions. Structure of Theorem and Their Types. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 45-47.
102. Usmonov M. T. Physical Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 58-61.
103. Usmonov M. T. Practical Security Management. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 71-74.
104. Usmonov M. T. Problem Solving In Primary Schools. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 72-83.
105. Usmonov M. T. Reproduction. The Laws of Reproduction. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
106. Usmonov M. T. Security Models. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 18-23.
107. Usmonov M. T. Solving Problems In Arithmetic Methods. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 58-61.

108. Usmonov M. T. Stenographic Protection of Information. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 31-35.
109. Usmonov M. T. Telecommunications and Network Security. International Journal of Academic Engineering Research (IJAER) ISSN: 2643-9085 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 57-61.
110. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Compatibility, Actions on Compatibility. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 10-13.
111. Usmonov M. T. The Concept Of National Security. International Journal of Academic and Applied Research (IJAAR) ISSN: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 73-75.
112. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Number. The Establishment of the Concept of Natural Number and Zero. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 18-21.
113. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Relationship. Characteristics of Relationships. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR) ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 38-40.
114. Usmonov M. T. The Concept of Size and Measurement. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
115. Usmonov M. T. The Emergence and Development of Methods of Writing All Negative Numbers. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 48-50.
116. Usmonov M. T. The Purpose, Function and History Of The Development Of Mathematical Science. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 8-17.
117. Usmonov M. T. True and False Thoughts, Quantities. International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAISR) ISSN: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 1-5.
118. Usmonov M. T. Virtual Protected Networks. International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 55-57.
119. Usmonov M. T. What Is Solving The Problem? Methods of Solving Text Problems. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 56-58.

120. М Усмонов - Academic research in modern science, 2022. КАК ПОСТРОИТЬ ЛИНИЮ В ПОЛЯРНОЙ СИСТЕМЕ КООРДИНАТ. Pages: 93-105.
121. UM Tulqin o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. DETERMINANTLAR NAZARIYASI. Pages: 232-248.
122. R Jo'rayev, M Usmonov - Solution of social problems in management and ..., 2022. OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATINING DOLZARBLIGI VA SAMARADORLIGI. Pages: 19-25
123. М Усмонов - Academic research in modern science, 2022. КАК ПОСТРОИТЬ ЛИНИЮ В ПОЛЯРНОЙ СИСТЕМЕ КООРДИНАТ. Pages: 93-105
124. М Усмонов - Development and innovations in science, 2022. ВЕКТОРНОЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЕ ВЕКТОРОВ. СМЕШАННОЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЕ ВЕКТОРОВ. Pages: 33-52.
125. М Усмонов - Models and methods in modern science, 2022. ДИСКРЕТНЫЙ ВАРИАЦИОННЫЙ РЯД. ПОЛИГОН ЧАСТОТ И ЭМПИРИЧЕСКАЯ ФУНКЦИЯ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ. Pages: 27-35.
126. М Усмонов - Инновационные исследования в науке, 2022. ИНТЕРВАЛЬНЫЙ ВАРИАЦИОННЫЙ РЯД. ГИСТОГРАММА ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЧАСТОТ. Pages: 43-52
127. М Усмонов - Международная конференция академических наук, 2022. ФОРМУЛЫ ДЕЛЕНИЯ ОТРЕЗКА В ДАННОМ ОТНОШЕНИИ. ФОРМУЛЫ КООРДИНАТ СЕРЕДИНЫ ОТРЕЗКА. Pages: 17-26.
128. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. YER OSTI SUVLARINING FIZIK XOSSALARI, KIMYOVIY TARKIBI, HARAKATI VA GRUNTLARNING SUV O'TKAZUVCHANLIGI, FILTRATSIYA QONUNI. Pages: 219-222.
129. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. VEKTOR VA SKALYAR MAYDONLAR. GRADIYENT VA YO'NALISH BO'YICHA HOSILA. DIVERGENSIYA VA ROTOR. SATH CHIZIQLARI. GRADIYENT MAYDONLAR. OQIMLAR. Pages: 172-187.
130. UM Tulqin o'g'li, QF Ergash o'g'li - IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY ..., 2022. FURE QATORI VA UNING TADBIQLARI. Pages: 21-33.
131. o'g'li, U. M. T. ., & o'g'li, Q. F. E. . (2022). FURE QATORI VA UNING TADBIQLARI. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 21-33. Retrieved from <http://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1152>
132. o'g'li, U. M. T. ., & o'g'li, Q. F. E. . (2022). DARAJALI QATORLAR. DARAJALI QATORLARNING YAQINLASHISH RADIUSI VA SOHASI. TEYLOR FORMULASI VA

- QATORI. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 8–20.
Retrieved from <http://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/jis/article/view/1151>
133. МТЎ Усмонов, ҲУМ Ўғли - Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary ..., 2022. РАВНОМЕРНОЕ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ВЕРОЯТНОСТЕЙ. 15-24
134. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi va ularni yechish usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
135. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Bir jinsli chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
136. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlar nazariyasi elementlari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
137. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli fazo. Yevklid fazosi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
138. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Matritsa rangi. Matritsa rangini hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
139. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Matritsalar va ular ustida amallar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
140. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Maxsud Tulqin o ‘g‘li Usmonov maqsudu32@ gmail. com Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Qarshi filiali. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
141. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Teskari matritsa. Teskari matritsani hisoblash usullari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
142. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Chiziqli operatorlar va ularning xossalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
143. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Xos vektorlari bazis tashkil qiluvchi chiziqli operatorlar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
144. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Kvadratlik forma va uni kanonik korinishga keltirish. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
145. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Arifmetik vektor fazo va unga misollar. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
146. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlarning skalyar ko ‘paytmasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
147. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Determinantlar nazariyasi. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
148. Mahsud Tulkin oglu Usmanov. (2021). Vektorlarning vektor va aralash ko ‘paytmalari. «Science and Education» Scientific Journal.
- 149.